

INVESTIGATION OF SPORTS ORIENTATIONS OF TEACHERS WHO WORK IN PUBLIC INSTITUTIONSⁱ

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to reveal the reasons of the teachers' tendency to sports activities in the 2016-2017 school year. This research is important in terms of revealing the teachers' sports activities approaches. The samples were generated among the teachers working in selected schools by using random sampling method. In the research, the survey technique used is quantitative research method. Developed by Gill and Deeter (1998) and adapted in Turkish by Erpehlivan (2008) the Sport Orientation Questionnaire (SOQ) is used. 386 teachers have participated in the research. The data were analyzed with the SPSS 22.00 packet program. Statistically significant differences were found according to professional experience and sports branches. Teachers with low vocational experiences tend to compete more in the sports activities that they are doing. In other words, the teachers are heading towards to sports activities for competition. Teachers with low or no vocational experiences are more likely to be successful in the sport branch that they are doing. So their goal is to succeed in the sports that they do. Individual and team sportsmen want to compete, win and be successful in the sport branch that they are doing. Also, those who play team sports tend to be more successful than those who don't participate in sports activities.

Keywords: sports orientations, teachers, sports

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1. Introduction

Public health depends on individual health. Individuals have to do their physical activities regularly in order to attain a healthy body (Hergüner, 1991). It is known that characteristics and qualifications teachers can attain may change depending on environmental conditions and that there are always regulations and searches for teacher training programs around the world therefore. Hence, to train qualified individuals that will determine the futures of societies is possible with highly-qualified teachers (Sışman, 2010). As well as possessing liberal education, field knowledge and professional skills, it is also very important for teachers to adopt “lifelong learning” idea towards contemporary developments and to use these skills in real life in order for them both to become qualified teachers and to keep in step with environmental changes (Karatas ve Güleş, 2013). According to Vallerand and Losier (1994), passion for sports has an effect on sport orientation.

Physical activity rate assessment on individual and social basis is very important in that it affects health status in many aspects (Saygın, 2003; Şanlı and Atalay Güzel, 2009). Therefore, it is a fact recognized for many centuries that doing sports contributes positive development in character traits, wealth, cooperation and improving skills (Shields and Bredemeier, 2007). If the educational value of sports is promoted well in any environment, education will be a significant element in competitive sports as well (Kohn, 1992). One of the most important goals to be paid attention to by coaches and educators is to establish the necessary environmental ground to promote the concepts of thinking ethically and morally and training character-wise and ideal sporters (Stoner, 2004). According to Karaca (1998), work, transportation, housing and sports activities of employed individuals and the aggregation of all these are at a low level in the aspects apart from sport activities. It is known that sports significantly contribute responsive and balanced development of the individual in physiological and psycho-social aspects (Hergüner, 1992). These all show that the goals and purposes of education and physical education and sports for the society correspond to each other at many points. We view being a socio-psychological role model as a practical method in educators’ responsibilities to sporters and individuals (Monacis et al. 2013). From this point of view, the idea that teachers’ sport orientation may affect their being taken as a role model occurs. Physical education and sport activities are regarded as a significant means of socialization in developed countries (Coakley, 1993).

Thus, the aim for this study is to address the reasons effecting the sport orientation of teachers working in public institutions. The study is important in terms of teachers’ being a model to their friends and students.

2. Method

2.1 Universe and samples

In this research quantitative research has been conducted by using survey technique. In this work the researchers were from Gaziantep Province, but the sample for this study were teachers chosen in a random way from determined schools (200 male, 186 female).

2.2 Data collection tool

Intention to determine the instruction of sports teachers are using standards guide for sports. This survey was developed by Gill and Deeter in (1988). In this work using several scales were discovered in three dimensions. These dimensions are competitiveness, guidance for success, and direction for target. And this three dimensions have different articles on the scale. This scale is adapted to Turkish by Erpehlivan (2008). In measuring 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19, 21, 23, 25 for competitiveness, 4, 8, 12, 16, 20, 24 for Goal Orientation and 2, 6, 10, 14, 18, 22 for Win Orientation. The Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient of the scale in the study was .93. Internal consistency scale value were used in this study worth in accordance with the result of analysis and the measure expanding Alpha for competitions power is (0.85), direction for target (0.75) and guidance for success (0.81).

2.3 Collection of Data

In this study, the questions in the survey form were adapted according to the teachers and the data were collected in the Gaziantep province between the years 2016-2017. The survey was conducted face to face by the researchers and the aim for this study was to explain it for.

2.4 Analysis of Data

The data gathered in the study were analyzed through statistical package software (SPSS 22.0) and the results were evaluated. At the outset, in order to form an opinion about the data, descriptive statistics including distributions of arithmetic average, standard deviation, frequency and percentage were checked. The data showed normal and homogeneous distributions. Independent samples test was used in examining the correlation between the data and demographic variables, in making a comparison between quantitative data and in making a comparison between groups in two-group cases. In more-than-two group cases, One Way ANOVA test was used while comparing the parameters between groups.

2.5 Findings

Table 1: The distribution of teachers' sport orientation value according to gender variable

	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	P
Competitiveness	Male	200	3.4827	.74707	-1.290	.198
	Female	186	3.5802	.73743		
Win Orientation	Male	200	3.2625	.98161	-.734	.463
	Female	186	3.3333	.90825		
Goal Orientation	Male	200	3.4525	.78554	-.902	.368
	Female	186	3.5269	.83515		

Table 2: The distribution of teachers' sport orientation value according to Marital Status variable

	Marital Status	N	Mean	SD	t	P
Competitiveness	Single	188	3.5090	.71257	-.534	.594
	Married	198	3.5493	.77223		
Win Orientation	Single	188	3.2411	.92551	-1.123	.262
	Married	198	3.3493	.96521		
Goal Orientation	Single	188	3.4362	.78821	-1.234	.218
	Married	198	3.5379	.82839		

Table 3: The distribution of teachers' sport orientation value according to educational status variable

	Educational Status	N	Mean	SD	t	P
Competitiveness	License	332	3.5083	.73148	-1.402	.162
	Postgraduate	54	3.6610	.80560		
Win Orientation	License	332	3.2791	.93830	-.901	.368
	Postgraduate	54	3.4043	.99717		
Goal Orientation	License	332	3.4588	.79840	-1.780	.076
	Postgraduate	54	3.6698	.86116		

Table 4: The distribution of teachers' sport orientation value according to age variable

	Age	N	Mean	SD	F	P
Competitiveness	18-25 age	109	3.4425	.73314	.929	.447
	26-32 age	107	3.5938	.71326		
	33-40 age	96	3.5529	.80169		
	41-47 age	66	3.5699	.73757		
	48 and over aged	8	3.2500	.55279		
Win Orientation	18-25 age	109	3.2722	.95168	1.141	.337
	26-32 age	107	3.2819	.88708		
	33-40 age	96	3.3889	.96811		
	41-47 age	66	3.3030	1.01312		

	48 and over aged	8	2.6667	.73463		
Goal Orientation	18-25 age	109	3.3960	.78068		
	26-32 age	107	3.4875	.82056		
	33-40 age	96	3.5556	.87180	.873	.480
	41-47 age	66	3.5732	.77467		
	48 and over aged	8	3.2500	.48795		

Table 5: The distribution of teachers' sport orientation value according to professional experience variable

	Experience	N	Mean	SD	F	P	Variation
Competitiveness	1-3 year	120	3.4397	.69343			1-2
	4-7 year	101	3.7212	.73055		0.005	2-4
	8-11 year	63	3.6435	.79681	3.727	*	2-5
	12-15 year	56	3.4025	.81526			3-5
	16 and over year	46	3.3428	.63364			
Win Orientation	1-3 year	120	3.2500	.92127			
	4-7 year	101	3.3911	.94382			
	8-11 year	63	3.4392	1.01878	1.240	.293	
	12-15 year	56	3.2232	.92784			
	16 and over year	46	3.1051	.92654			
Goal Orientation	1-3 year	120	3.3722	.74119			1-2
	4-7 year	101	3.6287	.85696			1-3
	8-11 year	63	3.6799	.87595	3.047	.017*	2-5
	12-15 year	56	3.4256	.84502			3-5
	16 and over year	46	3.2971	.64780			

Group 1: 1-3 year; Group 2: 4-7 year; Group 3: 8-11 year; Group 4: 12-15 year; Group 5: 16 and over year

Table 6: The distribution of teachers' sport orientation value according to sports variety variable

	Sports Branch	N	Mean	SD	F	P	Variation
Competitiveness	Individual sports	173	3.4384	.73992			
	Team Sport	141	3.6672	.76524	3.942	.020	1-2
	Not	72	3.4797	.67289			
Win Orientation	Individual sports	173	3.1696	.97737			
	Team Sport	141	3.4267	.94247	3.026	.050	1-2
	Not	72	3.3472	.84603			
Goal Orientation	Individual sports	173	3.3141	.79013			1-2
	Team Sport	141	3.7329	.79754	11.201	.000	2-3
	Not	72	3.4282	.76903			

Group 1: Individual Sport, Group 2: Team Sport, Group 3: Not (Aimless walk)

3. Discussion and Conclusions

In our study, the reasons for teachers working in public sector to show tendency to sports were examined. Statistically remarkable variations depending on professional experiences and branches of sports were observed. No such a prominent difference was observed in terms of age, gender, marital status and educational background variables.

There is no significant variation in genders. Sunay and Saracaloglu (2003) found in their study, which is similar in this respect, that gender is not so significant among the factors determining the branch of sports. However, different findings were also observed in the field. Jamshidi et al. (2011) found that sportswomen are more target-oriented than sportsmen and sportsmen are more competitive. According to Monacis et al. (2013), gender and the branch of sports indirectly effect the involvement in sports. Also, Flood and Hellstedt (1991) addressed the same judgement that men are more competitive than women. This distinction may as well be due to the cultural differences between societies involved in sports. Besides, there aren't so many studies recorded in foreign fields, on teachers concerning this matter.

Some differences have been observed in competitive capacity and target-orientation, depending on professional experience. Jamshidi et al. (2011) found in their study that sport orientation stipulates competitive anxiety. These studies correspond to our study. In addition, it was also observed in our study that increase in professional experience has a negative effect on sport orientation. Workload may have decreased sport orientation, and motivation therefore. Monacis et al. (2013) mentioned the suggestion that sport orientation increases motivation. Decrease in sport orientation may also be associated with gradual decrease in physical performance. Besides, professional responsibilities that one's age brings may have negatively affected the sport orientation. It can be inferred that teachers become more competitive and do sports in line with their goals, depending on their professional experiences. It's thought that this is due to the desire of teachers to prove themselves to their friends and their observing their physical and psychological status.

Significant variations depending on branch of sports were observed in our study results. It's clear that teachers who are involved in team sports are more competitive and target-oriented. This gives the impression that there is a high level of in-team competition. Jamshidi et al. (2011) found in their study that those doing team sports have higher scores. However, Jamshidi et al. (2011) couldn't find any difference between team sports and individual sports in sport orientation. In another study (Wakayama et al., 2002; Gareth et al., 2006), it was found out that sporters involved in individual sports, compared to team sports, are more competitive and win-oriented. Teachers doing individual and team sports desire to compete in the branches of sports

they're involved in, and to do sports target-oriented. As it is seen, various results were found in various studies. This is thought to be due to the sample group and cultural differences.

In conclusion, professional experience and branch of sport have a significant effect on teachers' sport orientation. Gender, marital status, educational background and age have had no effect on sport orientation of teachers. Competition and succeeding in a branch (target-orientation) are associated with teachers' sport orientation. It's recommended that administrators arrange and encourage activities that will motivate teachers to do sports.

References

1. Coakley J. (1993). Social Dimensions of Intensive Training and Participation in Youth Sports, Intensive Participation in Children's Sports, Cahili, B.R. and Pearl, A. J., Human Kinetics Publishers, Champaign. 77.
2. Erpehlivan Z. (2008). Spora Yönelim Envanterinin Türk Sporcuları İçin Geçerlilik Ve Güvenirlik Çalışması. Ege Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Sporda Psikososyal Alanlar Anabilim Dalı. Yüksek Lisans Tezi.
3. Flood S.E., Hellstedt J.C. (1991). Gender differences in motivation for intercollegiate athletic participation. Journal of Sport Behavior (JSB), 14(3): 159-167.
4. Gill D.L. and Deeter T.E. (1988). Development of the Sport Orientation Questionnaire. Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport, (59): 191-202.
5. Gareth J, Ken M, Peters D.M. (2006). Participation Motivation in Martial Artists in the West Midlands Region of England. Journal of Sports Science and Medicine, Combat Sports Special Issue (CSSI), 5: 28-34.
6. Hergüner G. (1991). "Çocuğun Spora Yönelmesinde Ailenin Rolü ve Önemi", Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi, (6): 87.
7. Hergüner G. (1992). Eğitim-Spor İlişkisi. On Dokuz Mayıs University, Faculty of Education Journal, (7): 61.
8. Jamshidi A., Hossien T., Sajadi S.S., Safari K., Zare G. (2011). The relationship between sport orientation and competitive anxiety in elite athletes, Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences, 30: 1161-1165.
9. Karaca A. (1998). "Fiziksel Aktivite Değerlendirme Anketi Güvenirlik ve Geçerlik Çalışması", Bilim Uzmanlığı Tezi, Hacettepe Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü.

10. Karataş S, Güleş H. (2013). Öğretmen Atamalarında Esas Alınan Merkezi Sınavın (KPSS) Öğretmen Adaylarının Görüşlerine Göre Değerlendirilmesi. Kuramsal Eğitim Bilim Dergisi, 6(1): 102-119.
11. Kohn A. (1992). No Contest. The Case Against Competition (2nd ed.). Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
12. Monacis L, Estrada O, Sinatra M, Tanucci G, De Palo V. (2013). Self-determined Motivation, Sportspersonship and Sport Orientation: A Mediation Analysis, Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences, 89: 461 – 467.
13. Saygın Ö. (2003). "10-12 Yaş Çocukların Fiziksel Aktivite Düzeyleri ve Fiziksel Uygunluklarının incelenmesi", Doktora Tezi, Marmara Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, 2003.
14. Shields D. L., Bredemeier B. (2007). Advances in sport morality research. In G. Tenenbaum & R. C. Eklund (Eds.), Handbook of sport psychology (3rd ed., pp. 662-684). Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.
15. Stoner M.E. (2004). Building ethics, character and sportsmanship in today's athletes. PSAHPERD, Spring, 30-31.
16. Sunay H, Saracaloğlu S. (2003). Türk sporcusunun spordan beklentileri ile spora yönelen unsurlar, Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi, 1(1): 43-48.
17. Şanlı E, Atalay Güzel N. (2009). Öğretmenlerde Fiziksel aktivite düzeyi - yaş, cinsiyet ve beden kitle indeksi ilişkisi. Gazi Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi, XIV, (3): 23- 32.
18. Şişman M. (2010). Türk eğitim sistemi ve okul yönetimi (2. baskı). Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
19. Vallerand R. J. and Losier G.F. (1994). Self-determined motivation and sportsmanship orientations: An assessment of their temporal relationship. Journal of Sport & Exercise Psychology, 16: 229-245.
20. Wakayama H, Watanabe E, Inomata K. (2002). Exploratory factor analysis of the Sport Orientation Questionnaire and the Task and Ego Orientation in Sport Questionnaire in a Japanese sport setting. Perceptual Motor Skills, 95: 1179-1186.

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